

NEXT GENERATION VACCINES AGAINST GASTROINTESTINAL MUCOSAL
PATHOGENS, USING HELICOBACTER PYLORI AS MODEL PATHOGEN

DELIVERABLE D9.2

Dissemination and communication toolkit

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5 - LINQ

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1. OBJECTIVE

The dissemination and communication toolkit has the aim to give guidance to the Vax2Muc consortium regarding dissemination activities and to guarantee a coherent presentation of the project on all communication channels used. By providing templates to be used for presentations, reports, meeting and internal documents, guidance documents and a graphic manual including the logos, the consortium has a comprehensive toolkit to achieve this goal.

All elements of the communication toolkit are accessible to the consortium via the project intranet LRZ Sync+Share.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOLKIT

Based on the Description of the Action, the dissemination and communication toolkit is to include a public project website as well as a set of templates for project presentations, deliverables, internal documents, meeting materials and other dissemination materials. These are being made available to all partners through the project intranet or have been sent to them via email.

In addition to the project specific dissemination and communication guidelines, the following reference documents from the European Commission are also available in the Communication & Dissemination folder on the Vax2Muc intranet:

- [Are you communicating your Horizon Europe project?](#)
- [Communication, dissemination & exploitation: what is the difference and why they all matter](#)
- [Acknowledge EU Funding](#)

LOGO AND COLOUR SCHEME

Before putting together the dissemination and communication toolkit, an appropriate **logo** and **colour scheme** were designed and made available for use in all dissemination-related materials.

Full logo

Simple logo

VAX2MUC COLOURS

Vax2Muc’s primary colours are dark petrol, light petrol, anthracite, grey and white. Secondary colours are green, orange, and beige. The colours can also be used in dithered hues.

Primary colours:

100%	85%	65%	45%	25%
100%	85%	65%	45%	25%
100%	85%	65%	45%	25%

Secondary colours:

100%	85%	65%	45%	25%
100%	85%	65%	45%	25%
100%	85%	65%	45%	25%

Based on this logo and colour scheme, further communication and dissemination materials were designed. The dissemination and communication toolkit currently includes: a project **PowerPoint master file**, a project **Word template**, a **poster template**, a **deliverable template**, and a **project fact sheet**. All templates have been created in a way that all documents and presentations relating to Vax2Muc have a coherent look and contain all information requested by the European Commission.

Information on how the colour scheme and logo should be used are summarized in the project’s **graphic manual**. In addition, the **editorial style guide** provides information on how to write clear and consistent content.

POWERPOINT MASTER FILE

WORD TEMPLATE

POSTER TEMPLATE

DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

<p>NEXT GENERATION VACCINES AGAINST GASTROINTESTINAL MUCOSAL PATHOGENS, USING HELICOBACTER PYLORI AS MODEL PATHOGEN</p> <p>DELIVERABLE D0.1 pre-GMP material</p> <p>CONTRACTUAL DELIVERY DATE: Feb-2024</p> <p>ACTUAL DELIVERY DATE: -</p> <p>RESPONSIBLE PARTNER: PIL, ISB</p> <p>Work Package: WP1: HYBRID ANTIGEN PRODUCTION FOR THE LEAD CANDIDATE Deliverable type: DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype Dissemination level: SEN – Sensitive Author(s): Name and surname (institution acronym) Reviewer: LMG Management GmbH</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>	<p>Vax2Muc – GA N° 101080486 D0.1 pre-GMP material</p> <p>Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</p> <p>General remarks</p> <p>Remember to prepare your Deliverable well before the submission deadline to give the coordinator/internal reviewer the chance to review the Deliverable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please hand in your Deliverable for review at least 10 days before the contractual due date. <p>The Deliverables in each project serve two main purposes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To serve as a reference document for other consortium members: The content of the Deliverable may serve as a basis for other tasks in the Work Package/ the project. To report on project progress: The Deliverables are checked and evaluated by the Funding Agency to assess project progress and the quality of outputs. <p>Therefore, please bear the following points in mind when preparing your Deliverable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Deliverable does not have to be lengthy; should work as a stand-alone document, this must contain all relevant information. Structure greatly enhances readability. <p>An executive summary, an introduction that explains the overall context of the deliverable, and a conclusion summarising the findings help others to grasp your message more easily.</p> <p>Therefore, we suggest sticking to the general structure suggested in this template. Please feel free to adapt the main part of the Deliverable ("Content") as you see fit.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Deliverable needs to be understandable and easily comprehensible for non-consortium members, too. <p>All Deliverables will be read by our project officer at the EC and potentially other readers (external reviewers if feasible in the context of a review meeting, or other interested researchers or members of the general public (if the Deliverable is "public"). They are most likely not aware of internal project allocations, services used, or related documents. Therefore, it helps to describe the content in a way that is targeted at these readers who are not aware of the overall project context.</p> <p>*** end of explanatory notes – please remove before submitting your deliverable ***</p>	<p>Vax2Muc – GA N° 101080486 D0.1 pre-GMP material</p> <p>1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY / ABSTRACT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Summarise the main purpose and findings of the Deliverable. <p>Add text here</p> <p>2. DESCRIPTION OF ACTIVITIES AND MAIN RESULTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This should be the main part of the deliverable. Add main report/ main findings. Add sub-headers where needed. <p>Add text here</p> <p>3. DEVIATIONS (if any)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Add any deviation occurred from the planned activities. <p>Add text here</p> <p>4. OUTLOOK (if applicable)</p> <p>Add a short outlook how the results will be used further in the project.</p> <p>Add text here</p> <p>5. REFERENCE (if any)</p> <p>Add references here</p>
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PROJECT FACT SHEET

A project fact sheet is available for download from the Vax2Muc project website (<https://www.vax2muc.org>) and the LRZ Sync+Share. The fact sheet provides a quick overview of the project's key information.

	<p>Fact sheet VAX2MUC 2</p> <p>Acronym Vax2Muc</p> <p>Full title Next generation vaccines against gastrointestinal mucosal pathogens, using Helicobacter pylori as model pathogen</p> <p>Programme HORIZON EUROPE</p> <p>Contract number Grant Agreement N°101080486</p> <p>Abstract</p> <p>To overcome antimicrobial resistance (AMR) compromising global public health, novel strategies to develop next generation vaccines against AMR pathogens are required. However, the development of effective vaccines is challenging for bacterial infections occurring at mucosal sites, in particular in the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. In this context, H. pylori is listed as high priority AMR pathogen and the most common chronic bacterial infection affecting half of the world's population with a high risk to progress into gastric cancer.</p> <p>Previous failures in H. pylori vaccine development approaches suggest that induction of mucosal immunity is required for protection. Thus, Vax2Muc will develop a rational prophylactic lead candidate against H. pylori in a straight-forward manner and directly evaluate this candidate for safety and immunogenicity in a phase I clinical trial, serving as proof-of-concept (PoC) for novel vaccine technologies developed in Vax2Muc. To induce long-term protective mucosal immune responses sustained by tissue resident memory T cells, we will apply our previously identified vaccine antigens, combined with potent adjuvants for a systemic prime, and implemented in an innovative oral-mucosal film for a mucosal pull. Vax2Muc will further advance GMP manufacturing and investigate and progress novel vaccine technologies and strategies tailored for mucosal application. We will evaluate our lead candidate and alternative approaches in pre-clinical models to define meaningful correlates of immunity and protection, which are still lacking for most of GI AMR infections.</p> <p>THUS, VAX2MUC WILL DELIVER</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a prophylactic vaccine candidate against H. pylori as PoC, and a wealth of knowledge and technologies that can be translated into the clinical development pipeline and are broadly applicable for various GIMMR mucosal pathogens to significantly benefit the challenging field of mucosal vaccination and finally reduce disease burden from AMR/GI diseases. 	<p>Fact sheet VAX2MUC 3</p> <p>Duration 90 months (21.07.2023 – 30.06.2033)</p> <p>Project funding 8.487.081,23 EUR</p> <p>Coordinator Prof. Marcus Gehrmann Institute for Medical Microbiology, Immunology and Hygiene, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany</p> <p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helmholtz Centre For Infection Research (HZI), Germany Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Denmark Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Lisbon (FPLU), Portugal LMU management GmbH (LMU), Germany Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Ireland Inovax Technologies A.S. (Inovax), Czech Republic University Antwerpen (UAntwerpen), Belgium IRISA Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA – CERCA), Spain University of Strathclyde (UoS), United Kingdom <p>Project management Dr. Inesena Finckenoh Institute for Medical Microbiology, Immunology and Hygiene, Technical University of Munich Email: inesena.finckenoh@tum.de</p> <p>Caroline Stäber LMU management GmbH Email: c.staeb@lmu-management.com</p> <p>Project website www.vax2muc.eu</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>
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GRAPHIC MANUAL

The graphic manual contains more information on the different variations of the logo, the Vax2Muc colour scheme and typography, as well as some design examples.

EDITORIAL STYLE GUIDE

The purpose of the editorial style guide is to help everyone who works with Vax2Muc to create clear and consistent content for all channels. The document is available for all consortium members in the intranet and divided into three sections:

- Writing goals and principles
- Grammar and mechanics
- Glossary

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Introduction viii

Vax2Muc will develop next generation vaccines to overcome the antimicrobial resistance of gastrointestinal mucosal pathogens compromising global public health. Therefore, Vax2Muc will develop, as a proof-of-concept, a prophylactic H. pylori vaccine candidate that will be evaluated in a phase I clinical trial. Moreover, it will advance GMP manufacturing, knowledge and progress novel vaccine technologies and strategies for optimised mucosal immunity in the gastrointestinal tract.

About this document

The purpose of this editorial style guide is to help everyone who works with Vax2Muc to write clear and consistent written communications. The document is divided into three sections:

- Writing goals and principles
- Grammar and mechanics
- Glossary

We use British English according to the [Oxford's Style Guide](#). If you are aware of any grammar rule that is not listed in the document or is in the wrong section of the document's style guide, please let us know at the following style guide:

- [University of Cambridge style guide](#)
- [Government of the United Kingdom's Style Guide](#)

Writing goals and principles ix

The guidelines provided in this section are mainly relevant for when you write for the Vax2Muc social media account (like website, X/Twitter and LinkedIn), that is when your target audience include the general public.

Target audience

Vax2Muc's website is highly topical and relevant to several different groups of people, institutions, and organisations. The project's key stakeholder groups include:

- Hospital partners (external)
- Scientific community (external)
- General public (internal)
- Industry (external)
- Patients (external)
- Regulatory authorities (external)
- European Commission/National Governments/Policyholders (external)

For a more thorough presentation of each target audience, see the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC).

Writing goals and principles

WRITING GOALS

Strive to use plain English, avoid unnecessary modifiers and vague language, and opt for a concise style. If full form is not available, use your best guess for the most likely intended meaning. Use parentheses and read every word just with others. Help everyone read better by grouping related items together and using descriptive headings and subheadings.

PLAIN ENGLISH

Write a sentence if it is shorter than a paragraph. Make it easy for the reader to get the information they need to know from your text by front-loading it (putting the conclusion first, followed by the what, how, where, when and why).

BE CONSISTENT

Stick to the copy formats and style points outlined in this guide.

Style tips

USE PROACTIVE

Avoid unnecessary pages.

ACTIVE VOICE

Use the active voice rather than passive voice. This will help the project write clearer, clearer content.

WRITING TIPS

Strive to use more positive than negative language.

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WRITING TIPS

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Grammar and mechanics x

Adhering to certain rules of grammar and mechanics helps us keep our writing clear and consistent.

If space is limited, such as when you write a X (Twitter) post, it is acceptable to break some of the rules listed here in order to make the text short enough to fit the character limit.

Abbreviations and acronyms

Specific abbreviations and acronyms will be used when the author mentioned in text, for instance: Technical University of Munich (TUM), unless it is well known, like UK or US.

Do not use full stops in abbreviations, acronyms, or initials, or in the middle of a sentence, like 'Mr', 'Prof' or 'Dr'.

Follow the international system of units as a guide for units of measurement.

PHRASING

Do not use phrases like "in order to" or "with a view to". Try to rephrase sentences to avoid the need to use "in order to" and "with a view to".

American and British English

Use UK English spelling. For example, use "organise" not "organize", "model" not "modelling", and "file" not "files".

American expressions, like "the letterhead" should use American English spelling.

Appositive

Use "and" rather than "or" unless it is a department's logo design or a company name.

Bold

Use bold sparingly - using too much will make it difficult for users to know which parts of your content they need to pay the most attention to.

Bullet points and steps

BULLETS

You can use bullet points to make a list easier to read. When using bullet points in body copy, make sure that:

- you always use a dash in line
- the bullet is under minor styling on the first line in line
- you do not put "or" or "and" after the bullet
- you do not put a colon at the end of a list if it is a list of items
- you do not put a colon at the end of a list if it is a list of items
- there is a full stop after the last bullet point if the last of the bullet point is not a complete sentence

Grammar and mechanics xi

Bullets should normally form a complete sentence following from the lead text. But it is not necessary to add a short phrase to clarify whether all or some of the points apply. For example, "You can only register a person where that is part of the following":

If the end of your bullet point is a complete sentence (or multiple sentences), use capital letters and punctuation. If your points are not structured as proper sentences, you do not need to end with punctuation and should preferably start each point with a lower case letter.

IRMS

Use the correct number of bullet points to guide a user through a process. You do not need a lead-in line and you can use bold and underline in steps. Steps and a full stop because each should be a complete sentence.

Capitalisation

Use lower case, such as possible. There is a tendency for people to capitalise words unnecessarily just because they are deemed "important". Avoid this.

Company names may feature unusual capitalisation (or lack of capitalisation), try to follow the company's convention, even if it looks odd.

DO NOT USE ALL-CAPS UNLESS FOR LEGAL NOTICES OR TO GET ATTENTION TO SOMETHING.

For a longer list of words that should or should not be capitalised, see [Cambridge's list](#).

Country names

Use the English equivalent (Germany, not Deutschland) and list any sequence of names in alphabetical order.

Contractions

They give your writing an informal tone, hence they are better suited for X (Twitter) posts than website copy and should be avoided when space is not an issue.

Dates

- Friday, 16 January 2023 (not 16th January)
- 2023, 2024, not 2023', 2023'
- 20th century not twentieth century (use 18th century only for adjectives like 18th century architecture or an increase in heavy drinking since 19 or 20 or 21st century, not a century)

Use two digits when representing a span of years, with the outer century (2020–25) and four digits (2020–2025) when spanning more than one century.

Dates are expressed as day/month/year, for example, 1 July 2023, or Monday, 1 July 2023 (under the column following the day of the week).

Email and web addresses

Email addresses and URLs should appear in lower case, for example contact@vax2muc.eu and www.vax2muc.eu. Do not include http:// or https:// at the beginning, and with a full stop if the address appears at the end of a sentence.

3. PROJECT WEBSITE

The public website www.vax2muc.eu was launched at the occasion of the project start and has seen a continuous development in its content since that day.

The website aims to reach a broad public and creating an ongoing awareness of the project's objectives and results. It has been developed in line with the project's corporate identity, thus ensuring that the site is appealing, efficient and easy to use.

As of today, the website contains the main page (landing page) and provides information divided into the following sub-pages.

About

The “About” subpage explains the project’s scope and objectives in more detail.

Activities

The project’s work plan consists of five scientific pillars which are described under “Activities”.

Team

The “Team” page lists all Vax2Muc partner institutions with key personnel involved in the project, including their contact details and pictures as well as their key responsibilities and role in the project.

Funding

The “Funding” subpage contains information on the project funding provided by the European Commission.

Publications

The section on project publications will support dissemination of outcomes and results. Following the principle of Open Science, all publications stemming from the project will be directly reachable from the website via embedded links to the full open access articles.

News

The “News” subpage will cover the latest information on all Vax2Muc related developments, feature announcements on interesting workshops, consortium meetings or content such as interviews with our consortium partners, members of the Scientific Advisory Board, or external experts in the field. It will be updated on a regular basis.

4. OUTLOOK

Throughout the project duration, the dissemination and communication toolkit will be maintained and adapted to include other materials whenever the need/occasion arises. This refers in particular to the website and further dissemination materials such as digital project brochures and flyers, which may need to be developed over the course of the project.